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Local policing and its implication for security in Anambra State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Situating security closer to the people, demanding accountability of security operatives and their agencies, and promotion of community-based crime prevention are all nuances of local policing. Anambra State in the eastern region did not allow operatives of Eastern Security Networks and Ebube Agu except Anambra Vigilantes Services alongside formal law enforcement agencies. It was against this background that this study engaged gap theory to investigate local policing and its implications on Anambra State, Nigeria. This study decomposed implications of local policing into policing accountability and community-based crime prevention in Anambra. This study engaged qualitative research design with reliance on secondary data, by reviewing publicly available archive documents concerning local policing, accountability of policing, community-based crime prevention and community policing. The literature was obtained through searches in publicly available material. Literature from non-serial publications, official reports, and conferences has been included particularly if they have been cited by other references in connection with local policing. Findings from the study showed that local policing as provided by Anambra Vigilante Service, devoid of the presence of Ebube Agu and Eastern Security Network shows accountability to the community. The study also established that local policing in Anambra has semblance of community-based crime prevention as the Vigilante and Formal security operatives collaborate in the line of duty. This study therefore recommends that the Federal Government should look beyond militarisation of South East and address genuine concerns raised by regional agitators as this will allow both formal and local policing to share common ground in accountability to host communities. This study also recommends that the total overhauling of the nation's security architecture will go a long way to allow local policing to be heard in security provision which will fast track community-based crime prevention as against the overcentralised commands of all formal security agencies.

Keywords: Community Policing; Community-Based Crime Prevention; Gap Theory; Policing Accountability

1. Introduction

Situating policing closer to the community through local policing, is a global phenomenon largely driven by human security approach as against State centric approach. The frontier of local policing could be seen extended by the inability of formal policing to adequately police the State in the face of rise in population, spike in crime and criminality. In Nigeria, efforts to further secure lives and properties has pushed States, regions and communities into creation of local policing via Vigilante services, Ebube Agu, and hunters associations amongst others. The need for local policing is further driven by its demand for accountability of both the security operatives and the security agencies to host community, and involvement of community-based crime prevention.

In Nigeria, the non-accountability of the formal security agents operatives and their agencies (Nigeria Police, Civil Defence Corps, Nigeria Drug Law Enforcement Agency, etc to the public has been largely responsible for the widening gap between these agencies and the public which is apparent in their inability to enjoy cooperation, supports and

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confidence of the populace (Inyang & Abraham, 2013; Onyedinefu, 2023). Local policing as rendered by Vigilante Services could be seen more accountable than formal security agencies (Onwuegbusi, 2017) and by extension the newly created Ebube Agu Security Network and the Eastern Security Networks (ESN). Where there is no existence of accountability of both formal and informal security operatives, lawlessness and anarchy that could endanger socioeconomic activities and safety of lives and properties could be enthroned.

Implication of local policing could be seen in its accountability for maintaining the public's confidence in the system (Walker, 2005). Unlike ordinary citizens, security operatives possess the broad powers needed to perform to arrest, detain, to search premises and seize items, to interrogate individuals, to stop assemblies, to check and even to restrict the movements of people during certain times and to use force and firearms in specific circumstances. In exercising such powers, they are required to act judiciously against committing human rights abuses since by their very nature, they interfere with the civil and political rights of individuals. In instances of violations, they are expected to be held accountable. Accountability for law enforcement operatives and agency they represent, for human rights violations evokes and entails the notions of lawfulness and legitimacy (Agbor, 2022).

Furthermore, local policing, where properly enabled could be seen catalyzing community base crime prevention. Community-based crime prevention is based upon the premise that private citizens can play a major role in preventing crime in their neighborhoods. Community-based crime prevention programs focus on increasing the participation of individual citizens, small groups, and voluntary community organizations in activities designed to reduce crime and to improve the quality of neighborhood life. Community-based crime prevention is deemed to be significantly influential in reducing delinquency within residential communities. Since local policing is situated within the community, tracking down variants and arresting recidivism will be of low challenge hence the need for security operatives within community to be well a tuned with their beats (Farrington & Welsh, 2012).

The creation of Ebube Agu was seen as an effort to water down the activities of the Eastern Security Networks which enjoys no legal backing. The ESN, which came up at a time of security dire needs; killing and harassment of the locals on farmland and kidnapping (Ede, 2021), opined that Ebube Agu creation, will be infiltrated by thugs and saboteurs to hunt the ESN and IPOB members, hence forecloses any common ground to operate together or co-exist as one must give way for the other (Oluwafemi, 2021), while the States also vowed to resist banditry as obtainable in ESN (Okoli & Alaribe, 2021). Amnesty International alleged extrajudicial killing on Ebube Agu of seven persons in Otulu in Oru East LGA of Imo state, calling for investigations (Uthman, 2022), amidst court proscription of Ebube Agu activities in Ebonyi State (Ugwu, 2023).

This study is situated in Anambra State, rich in natural gas, crude oil, bauxite, ceramic and an almost 100 percent arable soil, in terms of agro-based activities such as fisheries and farming, as well as land cultivated for pasturing and animal husbandry. The State has a large modern market located in Onitsha, which is the hub of the state's commerce and industry. Crime pattern ranges from unknown armed gangs, kidnapers, and activities of separatist groups which continually exacerbate security situation. The State is reputed for the creation of the infamous Bakassi Boys which was ill managed and used in politically motivated killings. Anambra. The 2011 National Crime Victimization Survey shows that most people in the South East region expressed high level of dissatisfaction with the manner police handle cases So much so that the level of distrust between the police and the communities they serve led to the formation of vigilante groups thus situating peoples' confidence in vigilante groups than the police itself. Anambra is one of the State in the South East that do not condone the existence of Ebube Agu militia nor Eastern Security Network rather Anambra Vigilante Group operatives (Attah, 2023).

Local policing demands for community accountability by security operatives could be seen in abeyance with activities of some vigilante groups, ESN, Ebube Agu and the formal policing structure. Non accountability to the host communities could be seen as a common indicators and this perspective has been underexplored hence the need for this study to fill the gap in literature as public accountability is a major requisite for local policing.

To achieve the objective of this study, the following research questions were answered:

- How does local policing influence community-based crime prevention in Anambra State?
- To what extent does local policing affect police accountability to local communities in Anambra State?
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2. Literature Review

2.1. Conceptual Review

2.1.1. Local Policing

Local policing occurs when law enforcement agencies are under the recognition and control of local government authority. Local policing could be identified by municipal, county, tribal, and regional police that derive authority from the local governing body that created it. The primary purpose is to uphold the laws of the jurisdiction, provide patrol, and investigate local crimes (International Association of Chiefs of Police, 2018). Local policing in the context of this study encompasses Vigilante of Nigeria, Ebube Agu Security Network as a regional local police, created by the five Eastern State Government. By virtue of the definition adopted, the Eastern Security Network (ESN) whose creation cannot be situated as an extension of State or local Government creation could be seen excluded, within the confine of the definition of local policing.

Implications of local policing when properly evolved will create a nexus between the community and law enforcement agencies working within the locality. Local policing also known as community policing demands for accountability by individuals operatives of an agency be it Vigilante, police, NSCDC, Ebube Agu and also generally as the Agency that deploy operatives to relate with the community. Police accountability assures that these actions take place in a uniform manner without discrimination or abuse. Policies, procedures, laws and various review processes exist to ensure that things such as arrests and trials are carried out with due process, and that police investigations are both thoroughly and objectively performed. Police accountability helps to assure that arrests are carried out with due process. (Sands, 2023). Local policing also drives community based crime preventive mechanism such that localized crime are quickly identifies, mitigated and neutralized (Farrington & Welsh, 2012).

2.1.2. Local Policing and Accountability

Security operatives accountability, describes the high public expectation placed upon law enforcement agencies, formal and informal security apparatus, and individual officers to act in a responsible and legal manner while upholding the law and controlling crime. This expectation is portends that all citizens will be treated equally under the law. It actually refers to interactions between law enforcement officials and the public. Systems that help assure police accountability include democratic elections, public reviews, internal reviews and processes for citizen reviews as law enforcement officers are expected to serve and protect individual citizens (Sands, 2023).

Without accountability, local policing will deteriorates with abuse of power, and negligence, and such will put the safety of entire communities at risk. Public accountability for local policing could be strengthen where there exist independent watchdog groups for sole purpose of monitoring local policing accountability accept of individual complaints from the community, as well as internal review processes, particularly in areas of civil rights violations that lowers the flag of accountability. Patrol officers need accountability when testifying about crimes that took place. Without high levels of police accountability, the likelihood of rogue officers, illegal search and seizure incidents, violations of civil rights and various other abuses of power are high. Local Policing accountability and confidence is necessary for public trust, as well as for public safety.

2.1.3. Local Policing and Community-Based Crime Prevention

Community-based crime prevention is deemed to be significantly influential in reducing delinquency within residential communities. Community based crime prevention in developed clime could be seen driven through informed initiatives such as such as Communities That Care (CTC), PACT (Pulling America's Communities Together), and Operation Weed and Seed are all examples of effective community initiatives (Farrington & Welsh, 2012). Since local policing is situated within the community, tracking down variants and arresting recidivism will be of low challenge hence the need for security operatives within community to be well a tuned with their beats.

Local policing could be deepened when it creates nexus for interaction; provision for youth with various developmental opportunities, which encourage participation and drives positive interaction with those reinforcing conventional behavior, assisting youth to acquire the vital skills needed to be successful, granting youth with constant recognition and acknowledgment for their effort, achievements, and overall improvement, acknowledging young person's effort and promote positive bonding, which elicits a feeling of attachment and commitment to those who provide meaningful recognition, and establish a clear standards for behavior through which youth become motivated to adopt the healthy behaviors of those they have established positive relationships with (Communities That Care, 2023).

2.1.4. Ebube Agu Security Outfits

Ebube Agu (fear of a lion), is the South East region security outfit, fashioned after the Southwest security outfit; Amotekun. Ebube Agu, with its headquarters in Enugu, is charged with the responsibility to coordinate all the activities of vigilantes in the Southeast, and to checkmate rising unrest in the region. The menace of unknown gunmen amidst insecurities in the region informed the decision of the Governors of the five Southeast states of Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu, and Imo and address the fast-deteriorating security situation in the region with the unveiling of a new security outfit codenamed Ebube Agu. Wanton abduction from Priest, Monarch, businessmen couple with Kidnapping, jail break activities, armed robbery in daylight could be seen slowing down the economic activities of the region hence the need for Ebube Agu Security Network (Njoku & Ogugbuaja, 2021).

All the five State Southeast governors, along with heads of security agencies in the region and the President General of Ohanaeze Ndigbo worldwide, agreed to maintain the joint security outfit of Ebube Agu. The meeting agreed on a ban on open grazing with the implementation to be carried out by security agencies, condemn terrorism and banditry in any part of Nigeria, particularly in the Southeast, condemned the burning of police stations, violent attacks on custodial centres with the unlawful release of inmates, and the killings including security personnel, natives/farmers and herdsmen. The communique also showed that the heads of all the security agencies in the South-East resolved to exchange intelligence in a seamless, effective new order that will help to checkmate crime in the zone. Mixed reactions welcomed the launching of Ebube Agu which is seen as an afterthought to water down activities of Eastern Security Network (ESN) of IPOB. IPOB insisted that there is no security outfit that can be thrown up in the zone aside from the ESN that would not be resisted by the people as such will incur the wrath of the ESN (Oluwafemi, 2021).

2.2. Empirical Review

Agbor (2022) thematically investigated accountability of law enforcement personnel for human rights violations in Cameroon. The study engaged thematic study research design solely on secondary data. Findings from the study submitted that that selective accountability has been the trend which puts the country at quite a distance from its international human rights obligations. Study was done in Cameroon using Cameroon data hence the need for similar study in Nigeria particularly Anambra to review the implication of local policing and accountability in the State.

Archbold (2021) thematically reviewed police accountability in the USA through different lens that police accountability has been enhanced in recent years at local, State, and federal levels. Results from findings showed that lack of 'buy-in' by some police personnel; limited research on the efficacy of common police accountability tools; lack of financial resources; lack of support and guidance by the federal government in recent years; and police unions. Study was done in developed clime while there is the need for similar studies in Nigeria, particularly Anambra as done by this study.

Olusegun (2016) investigated the joint efforts of the police and the communities in South-West, Nigeria in tackling the worrisome rates of crime. The study underpinned by broken window theory adopted empirical approach though related textbooks, journals, and other relevant publications. Findings from the study showed that the police force alone given their observable inadequacies cannot successfully tackle crimes in the society without adequate supports of the members of the community. The study emphasised that there exist a battered relationship between the Nigeria Police and their host communities as the people sees the police as one of the major threats to community security due to their extortion tendency slanged the "wetin u bring" which has caused gap between the Police and other stakeholders. The study only captured police community relationship in internal security while this study goes further to consider the accountability of local policing to the community.

Onwuegbusi (2017) employed mixed research method to examine the perception of the citizens in Anambra. The study engaged cross sectional survey design with structured questionnaire, Focused Group Discussion and In-depth Interview were employed on 540 adults aged 18years and above using the multi-stage sampling technique. Results from study showed that despite limitations of the vigilante members, the citizens of the State are still very supportive to them for the services they render to ensure a crime free society. Study though done in Anambra did not review accountability of local policing as provided by Vigilante Service vis a viz formal policing

Yusuf (2014) empirically investigated the imperatives for community policing in Nigeria. The study engaged secondary data across related publication, government reports, journals and online searches. Findings from the study revealed that there is the need for both the community and the Police to close up existing gap by disposing off the pre-conceived notion of enmity and rivalry that exist between them, they should cultivate every spirit of togetherness and see themselves as partners in the course of protection of lives and properties in the society. The study submitted that the role to be played by the community must always be significant. This study is country specific therefore there is the need for similar state specific study with more variables on local policing implication on Anambra State.

Ejiogu (2019) examined the nexus between community policing and the engagement of pastoral terrorism in West Africa considering the narratives, limitations, and strengths of adopting community policing. The study adopted a thematic approach on communities in West Africa plagued pastoral terrorism. Findings from the study showed that there exist the concept of disconnected communities with weakened social policing tendency and this made these communities to be susceptible to attacks. Study therefore projected the adoption of the concept of “connected communities” in order to enable a multilayered and all-involving intelligence community policing shield in individual communities under siege of the pastoralists, kidnapping and other forms of crimes and criminalities. This is a continental studies done on West Africa thus there is the need for State specific study to be done in Anambra State to examine local policing and its implication on accountability and community based crime prevention.

Onwuegbusi (2017) employed cross sectional survey design to examine public perception of the citizens of Anambra State on engagements of the vigilante groups in the State. The study engaged structured questionnaire, focused group discussion and in-depth interview to extract data which was analyzed with Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software. Findings of the study showed that residents of the State found the security services rendered by the Vigilante very supportive and timely in ensuring a crime free society in spite of a number of shortcomings and limitations of the vigilante. Study submitted that consistent and regular training of the vigilante members in the State will be the right path to go particularly if well interfaced with the formal security system. This study was carried out in Anambra solely in 2017 hence the need for extending the time period for comparative analysis.

Obidiegwu and Elekwa (2019) employed purposive sampling technique to assess the level of collaboration between vigilante security group and the Nigerian police in arresting insecurity in Abia State. The study engaged 648 Town Union Executives (TUEs) and 78 Policemen in 10 Local Government Areas with registered vigilante units, while data collected were analyzed using mean and t-test statistics. Results from the study showed that there exists collaboration between the vigilante services and the Nigerian police force to minimize crime to a high extent. Study thus emphasised that the government should enhance more collaborative platforms between the vigilante and police to enable them embark on joint deliberations, decision making and actions as such will promote harmony, teamwork, efficiency and effectiveness among the vigilante and the police for greater crime control and protection of lives and properties. The study was done using Abia State data hence there is the need for similar but extensive study to be done using Anambra State data.

Ordu and Nnam (2017) analysed current developments in community policing in Nigeria. Community policing is a strong partnership, collaborative efforts of police and members of the public with a view to protecting lives and property at the neighbourhood level. Study opine that with effective community policing in place, public safety is guaranteed, helps police to identify, analyse and incisively address societal problems with full supports of community members. Police-community partnership, police-community information sharing, and police involvement in community affairs as salient strategies for effective community policing. The study submitted that bribery and corruption, human rights abuse, public loss of trust/confidence, meddlesome attitudes of political godfathers in police-community affairs, lack of visionary schemes, and unnecessary use of coercion and threats to enforce public compliance with rules, have frustrated every effort to improve and stabilise police-public co-operation which is a precondition for effective community policing.

2.3. Theoretical Review

2.3.1. The Gap Theory

This study is underpinned by the gap theory as propounded by George J. Thomson (Thomson, 2006). The gap theory argues that there is a widening ‘gap’ between the police and the community in too many areas. People, corporate entities, trade association including youths who had been mistreated by the Police withdraw from the police and are never eager to help the police and live in resentment of the Police. Until Police officers are taught to care for the people, the ‘gap’ increases. The deviants and crooks in the society benefit from the ‘widening gap’ between the police and the people. However, the better the police treat the people, the safer they feel and the more the ‘gap’ closes. As the ‘gap’ closes, it closes on the criminals and the deviant in the community.

Police-community relationship training will therefore promote trust and confidence building between the police and the people in preventing crime in the community. According to (Thompson, 2006), the quality of contact with the people by the police affects the way the people in turn perceive the police. Therefore, to improve on the quality of contacts with the public, the police should be thought about the ‘90-10 principle’ of the community. Thompson, (2006) stated that in the worst areas of the cities, 90 percent of all the people in those communities are good, hard-working, decent folks trying to make a living with dignity. Ten percent are the murderers, drug dealers, kidnappers and other criminal elements that need to be taken off the streets.

However, the problem with police work is that too often, 90 percent of police contacts are with those 10 percent who are the deviant and crook. So this distorts police view of the community. The police easily become cynical and tend to 'go to war' against those communities rather than taking on a protective role. This according to (Thompson, 2006) explains why the police are most hated where they are most needed. People mistreated do not give intelligence to those who mistreated them. So adequate community policing training will help close the gap of mistrust and lack of confidence between the police and the people and make police more humane in carrying out their services within the community.

3. Methodology

This study adopted qualitative research design to examine local policing and its implication for security in Anambra State. The study engaged involvement of policing accountability and community-based crime prevention as possible implication for local policing in Anambra State. The literature was obtained through searches in publicly available material. Literature from non-serial publications, official reports, and conferences has been included particularly if they have been cited by other references in relation to community policing.

4. Discussion of Findings

The review of literature showed that the local policing as provided by Anambra Vigilante Services devoid of Ebube Agu and Eastern Security Network shows accountability to the community. This could be explained by the State government position not to recognise Eastern Security Network in Anambra and little or no less commitment to the regional security outfit of Ebube Agu, hence the local Vigilante could be seen more accountable to the community where they operate. This findings align with the previous works of Agbor (2022); Archbold (2021); Olusegun (2016); Onwuegbusi (2017); Yusuf (2014) which showed poor accountability to host communities by security agencies in discharging their local policing function.

The result gotten from empirical literature also establish that seeming ability to evolve community-based crime prevention by local policing particularly Anambra Vigilante Service traceable to the state security where commands and controls of local policing adopted is situated in each community as against formal policing structure that is unitary and far from the community. This finding is consistent with the findings in the previous work Ejiogu (2019); Onwuegbusi (2017); Obidiegwu and Elekwa (2019); Ordu and Nnam (2017).

5. Conclusion

This study concluded that local policing efforts should be amplified by overhauling the security architecture of Nigeria such that the dominance of the military will be scaled back. Paramilitary and quasi state actors in the security architecture will allow security to be situated closer to the people. This will go a long way to enhance policymakers to deliver good governance to the people of Anambra State.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are made;

- That the Federal Government should look beyond militarisation of the Southeast and address genuine concerns raised by regional agitators as this will allow both formal and local policing adopted in regions to share common ground in accountability to host communities. Since military in local domain are not accountable to host community.
 - That the total overhauling of the nation's security architecture will go a long way to allow local policing to be heard in security provision which will fast track community-based crime prevention as against the overcentralised commands of all formal security agencies at the centre.
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Compliance with ethical standards

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